

Circumventing Censorship on the University Campus Through the Analysis of a Dramatic Text

Romain Dédjinnaki Hounzandji

Université d'Abomey-Calavi, Abomey-Calavi, Benin

drhaumain@gmail.com

Translated by Georgina Collins

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13696815.2024.2321974>

Abstract

In 2016, Beninese police moved onto the university campus in Abomey-Calavi to control the violent student demonstrations which led to the invalidation of the 2015–16 academic year in the Faculté des Lettres, Arts et Sciences Humaines, and the turmoil that turn of events subsequently risked causing. This local form of censorship was amplified by nationwide breaches of freedom of speech and opinion. It is worth asking, therefore, how the university reacted to all this. Indeed, certain teachers and students used educational activities as a pretext for overcoming the drastic restrictions to their freedoms. Hence, in the context of these pedagogical activities, this study aims to show that the analysis of purposefully selected dramatic fiction can be employed in the critique of genuine infringements to freedom, and also in the identification of ways in which individuals overcome those infringements. Participant observation and the concept known as the “Horizon of Social Expectation”, as applied to dramaturgical analysis, serve as a methodological basis for this two-part study of the aforementioned educational activities. The first part offers a brief description of the political context, the strategic positioning of contributors and their respective levels of involvement in the pedagogical experience. This contextualisation then leads to the second part: a presentation of the results of analysis conducted on paratextual data and the two dramaturgical categories of the theatrical text itself.

Keywords: UAC, censorship, pedagogical activities, dramatic fiction, Horizon of Social Expectation, students, readers

Introduction

In 2015–16, the Université d'Abomey-Calavi (UAC; University of Abomey-Calavi) in Benin saw a crisis marred by violent student demonstrations. For one of the university's 35 training and research units, the Faculté des Lettres, Arts et Sciences Humaines (FLASH; Faculty of Literature, Arts and Humanities), these events led to the invalidation of that academic year. This invalidation involved over 23,000 students, meaning that around 35.5 per cent of the total number of learners registered at UAC (UAC 2017, iv) were not entitled to an academic result. To control the misconduct that led to the invalidation and to limit the risk of further trouble, a police taskforce set up an HQ on campus, carrying out regular patrols and quickly intervening in any attempt to cause unrest.

The strongest visible sign of local censorship was therefore the presence of state police on campus, and, on a national scale, this was intensified by a more diffuse censorship sustained by violations of freedom of opinion and expression. Leaders may have professed to work towards strengthening democratic principles and institutions through political rhetoric, but in reality, they constrained to silence any voices that were discordant and far too critical through a very biased court ruling, among other measures, that deprived people of certain freedoms. It is thus worth asking how students and teachers reacted to this local and national censorship. This issue is all the more interesting as, in times past and in light of research, important links have been established between socio-political change and student action at the Université Nationale du Bénin (National University of Benin), which, in 2002, became the Université d'Abomey-Calavi.¹ In view of this correlation, it was likely that some teachers and students, incapable of passivity, took advantage of the unchallengeable “pretext” of pedagogical activities in general and, more specifically, the analysis of a play as an unexpected way to overcome the barriers imposed by censors on their freedom of expression and opinion. Hence, this study aims to show that, in the strict context of pedagogical activities, analysis of intentionally selected dramatic fiction can serve to critique genuine violations of freedom, and to identify the means used to combat them. Participant observation and the concept of a “Horizon of Social Expectation” applied to dramaturgical analysis serve as a methodological focal point for this study. Participant observation has been chosen because I was directly involved in the pedagogical activities that focused on the analysis of the play and that were aimed at opening up free speech, if only for the duration of teaching. In the fictional world, the dramatic text under consideration incorporates scenes featuring the strict control of free

speech, similar to real-life situations experienced by the students and their teacher. Hence, the readers seek to satisfy certain desires and expectations, if notionally, while analysing the dramatic text. Therefore, the concept of a Horizon of Expectation, consubstantial with the theory of reception aesthetics, seems pertinent in trying to respond to the needs of a mutually enlightening relationship between the world of dramatic fiction and that of real life, experienced by the main participants in the educational activities that form the basis of this study. These activities relate to *Le Compte-rendu (The Report)* by Togolese writer Bodi Banche Bodelin (2015). They also involve a Theatre Studies² lecturer and a group of second-year undergraduate literature students at UAC during the 2018–19 academic year.³

There are two parts to this study. The first comprises a brief introduction to the political context, the perspectives of the main contributors and their particular levels of involvement in this pedagogical experience. This contextualisation then leads to a presentation of the results of analysis conducted, first, on paratextual data, and, second, on two dramaturgical categories of the theatrical text itself.

Perspectives in Active Pedagogy in a Liberticidal Context

In the recent history of UAC, the invalidation of the 2015–16 academic year in FLASH⁴ remains a landmark occurrence. In the sequence of events immediately leading up to this invalidation, and even before that, the boycott of exams at the end of the first semester by FLASH students would be one of the most notable. They demanded prior guarantees that a catch-up session would be organised for students who would otherwise not have validated teaching units at the normal end-of-semester evaluation. Those in charge of student organisations then expanded action to all UAC campuses to put pressure on heads of faculty and the rector's office. The call to boycott pedagogical activities spread across the university, and “acts of premeditated violence, incitement to violence, terrorism and gross assault”⁵ were not uncommon. Indeed, this modus operandi brought tension to such a high level that, at the request of the rector's office, a police taskforce set up permanent headquarters on campus. It carried out regular patrols to disperse the smallest of crowds and anticipate any unrest. This presence lasted until March 2020, when the state's police force had to withdraw from campus following an incident that cost a student's life.⁶

Between the motion to boycott exams in 2016 and the withdrawal of police in 2020, various events punctuated life on campus. In October 2016, student organisations were suspended by

the government owing to a decision taken by the council of ministers. A year later, they were given authorisation to operate once again, but they were now governed by a new decree limiting the most “audible” forms of action – in other words, more dynamic unrest and demonstrations. This same diffuse censorship also affected the higher education teachers’ unions. As with all trade unions in the Republic of Benin, they were subject to a new law concerning the right to go on strike. Article 13 stated:

When procedures are respected, the right to strike is exercised under certain conditions whereby the duration cannot exceed: ten (10) days in the course of the same year; seven (07) days in the course of the same semester, and two (02) days in the course of the same month. Irrespective of duration, the cessation of work during the course of a day is considered to be a full strike day.

The impact of this set of laws and decrees aimed at student organisations and teachers’ higher education unions was inevitable: activism, protest movements and other forms of petition unsurprisingly lost traction, and there were tangible effects such as student union general meetings becoming increasingly scarce, and numbers of active and engaged members of the joint union for teachers in higher education reducing at a rate of knots. Henceforth, in the absence of regular major demonstrations and a lack of communication through physical contact with activists, student organisations and teachers’ unions sometimes published motions to protest or strike where the tone and content offered reliable indicators of the severity and hostility of the powers that be. For example, on 4 April 2018, the three student organisations at UAC⁷ published a joint motion to strike in which they lambasted “the government’s determination ... to implement the suicidal plan to compromise the freedom of associations on campus” and “the different measures taken whereby the only objective is the worsening of student living and studying conditions”. Hence, among other things, they demanded:

the pure and simple repeal of decree no. 2017-155 of 10 March 2017 bearing criteria for the allocation of grants for academic study, and the operational decrees drawn up for this purpose; the immediate and unconditional repeal of decree no. 2017-485 of 2 October 2017 defining the methods by which student organisations may collaborate with the State and authorities of State universities in the Republic of Benin and drawn up or in the process of being so for this purpose; ... the immediate and unconditional

withdrawal of armed men from our state universities in the Republic of Benin; ...
respect for academic freedom.

These extracts from the joint motion to strike clearly outline the socio-political context, discussed thus far in this study, of the crises that related to the invalidation of the 2015–16 academic year.

In view of this socio-political context, it seems that real-life events experienced by UAC teachers and students reading the dramatic fiction under consideration here have resulted in two main topics for discussion: the threat of plummeting living and studying conditions and the drastic restriction of basic freedoms in the course of regulatory and institutional reforms.

In the eyes of the teacher who initiated the process of circumventing censorship through the analysis of dramatic texts, these restrictions imposed on the freedom of association and expression were a significant step backwards for Benin, a country with a reputation for being a model of democracy in West Africa since 1990. This view was shared by some of the students involved in the pedagogical experience who were activists in specific branches of the university's central student organisations. For a larger number of students, as long as lessons took place, they did not care that their freedom may be restricted and studying and living conditions severely threatened.

For the teacher, the perspective of this second group of students was the most concerning, especially as it signalled a curious lack of effort to understand the world and an inability to exercise critical judgement on what was happening around them. Without doubt, this lethargy was an immediate secondary effect of this repression of freedom of speech. Without distancing himself from the lesson's main objective, to analyse theatre, the teacher questioned how he could use a piece of dramatic fiction to open up these young and developing minds to the political realities to which they were so indifferent, that affect their lives as citizens and students, and about which they should form their own opinions. The solution he identified was to guide them, through successive instructions, in the close analysis of a play about a dictatorship through the lens of political satire. Analysis was divided and discussed across four classes: the first targeted the paratext, the Horizon of Social Expectation was covered in the second session, and the third and fourth looked at characters and plot respectively. Clearly, the number of activities varied depending on the aims and content of each class. For each activity, the role of the teacher was limited to offering instructions likely to help students

focus on the textual and extratextual data and conduct satisfactory analysis that would help them take a stance they could justify. For the teacher, it was important not to standardise the students' perspectives on the issue of restricted freedoms. Instead, the aim was to encourage the emergence and/or expression of different viewpoints that could either add different nuances to his own or even contradict them, provided they were supported by their reading in conjunction with the analysis of data pulled from the theatre paratext and the dramatic text itself.

Escaping Censorship: *Le Compte-rendu* Text and Paratext

Le Compte-rendu (*The Report*) was written and performed for the first time in 1989 and published later in 2015, establishing Bodi Banche Bodelin as a writer with a creative vein that Togolese academic and playwright Ayayi Togoata Apédo-Amah (1997) refers to using the term “*tractographes*” (tractographies). He applies this neologism to playwrights who focus on satirising African dictatorships or democracies. Some of these works have been the subject of research by academics such as Pierre Médéhouégnon and Romain D. Hounzandji, among others, highlighting aspects of these blacklisted dictatorships and the dramaturgical methods used to criticise them. In terms of UAC teaching, especially in the Faculté des Lettres and the École Normale Supérieure (selective school and research establishment), many works demonstrating these tractographies have served as learning materials for educational activities. There are many such texts, including *Le Carrefour* (*Crossroads*) by Togolese writer Kossi Efoui and *Chemins de croix* (*Ways of the Cross*) by Kangni Alem, also from Togo; then there are Beninese writers Ousmane Alédji and Daté Atavito Barnabé-Akayi, who wrote *Cadavre mon bel amant* (*Corpse My Handsome Lover*) and *Les Confessions du PR* (*Confessions of the PR*, meaning the President of the Republic) respectively. Hence, such teaching materials and the study of political satire in plays are not unprecedented at UAC. But the aim of this present study is very specific in terms of its analysis. It should be remembered that its objective is to show that in university theatre studies classes, the analysis of purposefully chosen dramatic fiction can have an impact beyond initial pedagogical objectives to bypass censorship and critique diffuse or flagrant political dictatorship.

In fact, *Le Compte-rendu*, the play chosen to illustrate the process of analysing a theatre text, is all about the judgement of Histoire (History). Indeed, infuriated by the same old recriminations from Le Plaignant (The Plaintiff) against those in power, History decides to

descend among humans to pass his judgement upon the protagonists of “the tragicomic madness of the bloody and farcical reign of autocracy and obscurantist military dictatorship” (Ayayi 2015, 11). Resident dictator Le Soldat (The Soldier) defends himself against The Plaintiff’s and Le Poète’s (The Poet’s) accusations that he is a terribly immoral and gruesome character. And to escape the clutches of History, he primarily relies on the endlessly unfailing support of a tormented population that is both exploited and also responsible for paying the tyrant endless compliments. However, Le Peuple (The People) really need to speak out so that judgement can take place and some finality can be achieved. To eradicate the problem, History strips The Soldier of his authority and power. The People, thus liberated, rebel and shout: “This is the final scene of a comedy that’s lasted far too long.” The People want the now defeated dictator to pay for his crimes, but History calls for reason and intelligence to end the cycle of stupidity.

In terms of the analysis of this play, the teacher first chose to explore the play’s paratext with his students.

Liberticidal Power: Linking the Co-text with the Student-Reader Experience

At the start of the class on paratextual analysis, the teacher presented two key approaches to this fundamental concept: those of Jean-Marie Thomasseau⁸ and Michel Pruner.⁹ The teacher then finished his presentation with an evaluation: the content Pruner relates to the concept seems distinctly preferable to Thomasseau’s approach,¹⁰ insofar as the first is very much in line with tradition regarding the forms and functions of the paratext, and is therefore proven by literary criticism.¹¹ However, the teacher suggested that the students integrate initial stage directions with the content allocated by Pruner to the theatrical paratext. He believed that they could well be seen as part of the architecture of this “‘vestibule’ that provides everyone with an opportunity to enter, or to retrace their steps” (Genette 1987, 4). Hence, in the context of this particular class, adding initial stage directions to the title and accompanying discourse produces what is being defined here as the content of the paratext. While it is true that this definitional consensus could be discussed more, the reason the teacher chose to dedicate a whole session to the analysis of the paratext was because this opening to the dramatic text ideally serves as a stimulus to establishing the reader’s Horizon of Expectation as long as that reader can observe elements of reality expressed by and in the play’s text.

By applying the above instructions to *Le Compte-rendu* by Bodi Banche Bodelin, students were able to observe that the clear components of the paratext are, in order: the title followed by a list of awards, epigraphs, initial stage directions and preface.

Through analysis, the students noted that the title of the play, *Le Compte-rendu*, is, in itself, aponic, especially when taken in isolation. No doubt intended, this deficiency served only to pique the students' curiosity, tempting them to read the information supplied on the play's awards and the two epigraphs so hopefully they could gather more evidence to help formulate a hypothesis of meaning. The two prizes given to the play can be read on the front cover, below the title.

Le Compte-rendu was a "Finalist in the 17th RFI InterAfrican Awards"¹² and won the "3rd FESTHEF (Democracy Prize from the American Cultural Centre in Lomé)".¹³ These elements of the paratext are followed, on one of the flyleaves, by two epigraphs that take a satirical tone: "Woe betide anyone like Candide, who sings all over that everything is for the best on this shambolic continent!" (Bodelin 2015, 8). Then, below: "Here, time makes a fool of everything, it even mocks the most generous of dreams" (ibid., 8). From a comparative review of these components, it can be seen that, while the second prize on the list focuses on democracy – on the face of it, a synonym for stability and development – the two epigraphs indicate a flagrant lack of such traits, for they appear to reference a prevailing misfortune, implied in the term "shambolic continent" and again in the phrase "it even mocks the most generous of dreams".

The existence of misfortune, which emerges like a hypothesis of meaning, is strengthened by information extricated from reading the initial stage directions. According to the learners' observations, the list of characters and especially the detail provided on each one of them make the students realise that these individuals are, in all likelihood, involved in a certain chaos of which the student-readers later discover the true meaning in the main body of Bodelin's play. Upon reading the initial stage directions, the students, following their teacher's instructions, realise that the characters do not share between them a community, social status or concern. The initial information on The Plaintiff and The Soldier is characteristic of this division. In the list of characters, the first is introduced as "a young man of around thirty years old, in faded blue jeans and a t-shirt upon which is written 'This land of Africa'" (Bodelin 2015, 9), while the second description is of an impressive and formidable

character: “The Soldier: Grand, imposing, in battledress. On his epaulettes, the symbol of death; chest covered with medals, small bones hanging from them” (ibid., 9). Straightaway, the initial stage directions provide an image of a sinister character, at the very least through the distinctions he is wearing: epaulettes embellished with the symbol of death, bones hanging beneath the medals. This description is the origin of The Soldier’s oppositional relationship with The Plaintiff: through the name he bears, The Soldier is implicitly designated as the one against whom The Plaintiff will make recriminations.

The final piece of the paratextual fabric of *Le Compte-rendu* is the preface by Ayayi Togoata Apédo-Amah, entitled “Theatre at the Seat of History’s Judgement” (2015, 11). It casts more light upon the promised direction of the dramatic text itself. The preface writer unveils the subject of the play: a supreme judge named History presides over the trial of political and public characters obliged to recount their actions before the people. And the preface reveals something even more interesting: the author’s aesthetic choices and what motivates them:

Plays like *Le Compte-rendu* that revived Togolese theatre from 1989 to 1990 deserve a special place among Togolese literature, for they have been works of political combat dedicated to the liberation of a subjugated and zombified population. The bluntness and violence of language are features of these plays in which there has been a deliberate choice of no-frills expression, to challenge the censorship and especially the self-censorship prevailing at the time of single and iniquitous party rule, of “animation” (singing and dancing to the glory of the resident dictator) and of the Timonier National.¹⁴ (Apédo-Amah 2015, 14–15)

According to the preface, the register of Bodelin’s play adopts a type of mockery and caustic wit used as a form of refusal to relinquish one’s rights amidst the prevailing censorship. This information extracted by the students from *Le Compte-rendu*’s paratext, along with the learners’ brief analysis, revealed the components that give structure to the co-text, something that Popovic says comes from “the links the text establishes with available knowledge and discourse in the sociocultural space, which constitute the materials with which and upon which it works” (2014, 156). The co-text of Bodelin’s play is defined by the misfortune of a youth daring to challenge a liberticidal and mortiferous power, despite those young people being robbed of their dreams due to authoritarian leadership. It is possible to compare this co-

textual information with aspects of reality experienced by the students and their teacher at UAC, and in Benin more generally.

Of course, in Bodi Banche Bodelin's play, the dramatic space is not a university campus. However, real circumstances brought about by authoritarian leadership and its effects, including repression, restrictions, even the removal of freedoms, constitute, if not a bridge, then a point of connection between the co-text of *Le Compte-rendu*, which is extricated from the analysis of the work's paratext, and the experience of participants in the pedagogical activities surrounding the analysis of this dramatic text. Such a link no doubt fertilised the student-readers' encounter with the text from this Togolese playwright. This encounter, for them, seemed to be a real opportunity to satisfy the expectations they had started to develop with their teacher at the start of the second class on *Le Compte-rendu*.

Circumventing Censorship and Vicarious Satisfaction

The expectations constructed by the class as a group can be followed and understood relatively easily by referring to a concept known as the Horizon of Social Expectation,¹⁵ which is fundamental to reception theory. Clarifications supplied by the teacher helped students remember that the Horizon of Social Expectation is nourished by the situational context of each reader or spectator, regarded, of course, as individuals, but principally as both the component and product of a social complex. This complex functions as a higher authority that modulates and sometimes dictates to the public the interests it pursues, the needs it expresses and the expectations it holds. Since these interests, needs and expectations are dynamic, it also means that everything is shifting and surprising the meaning potential with which the public is capable of (re-)permeating a cultural work. This is particularly so because "African publics, readers, viewers, listeners, spectators, and users make meanings in ways that cannot be pinned down or predetermined and in ways that are often unpredictable" (Bush and Ducournau 2020, viii). In the study discussed here, the public is made up of literature students guided by instructions from their teacher-facilitator.

In the class session dedicated to determining a common Horizon of Social Expectation, two important activities were observed. The first helped students to recall, on the one hand, observations made throughout the analysis of the play's paratext, and, on the other hand, facts related to their situational context as university students and additionally as individuals in a country subjected to sometimes diffuse, sometimes militaristic censorship of spaces and

possibilities for free public expression of opinion. Having considered these parameters, the second activity consisted of gathering and summarising students' diverse responses to the question: what use do you hope that reading this play might be on a campus and in a country where spaces for free expression of ideas and opinions are subjected to severe restrictions, diffuse in some cases, militaristic in others? When looking at a summary of their responses, three issues stood out as structuring the concrete expectations generated by the "interests, desires, needs and experiences" of these student-readers. The most recurrent expectation articulated was to find, in the analysis of a fictional world centred on the trial of a despot, a good pedagogical pretext for criticising the leading contributors to real-life censorship. The student-readers also hoped that, through the means of these dramatic events, they might feel liberated from present-day censors through the demise of the fictional despot, despite not experiencing this freedom in their current reality. Finally, the students expected to derive ideas and strategies from the play that could contribute to gradually developing their awareness, looking to the inevitable deterioration of mechanisms used in real-life censorship. These three issues provided a sense of direction to the next part of the play's analysis, which is related to setting pedagogical objectives and targeting theatrical categories to study and help achieve those objectives.

With the overall aim of being liberated from the censorship conferred upon them, the student-readers, under the guidance of the teacher-facilitator, initially endeavoured to produce a tropic discourse¹⁶ that was disparaging of the primary contributors to censorship; they then attempted to satisfy, through catharsis, their desire for freedom of speech through the demise of the fictional despot; finally, the teacher undertook to supply the student-readers with a heightened awareness of ideas related to a possible breakdown of the mechanisms used in real-life censorship. These objectives, it must be remembered, stemmed from the Horizon of Social Expectation and its related public, which, in this case, was a group of 2018–19 second-year undergraduate literature students studying the course entitled "Theatre Text Analysis". To achieve these objectives, the learners focused on character and dramatic plot for their dramaturgical analysis. To support the choice of these two categories, several ideas were taken from the theoretical concepts introduced to the students in the context of teaching theatre text analysis, well in advance of reading *Le Compte-rendu* by Bodi Banche Bodelin.

In fact, the students recalled that, in the play, the character is presented as a semantic and semiotic complex: he is situated at a “crossroads of meaning” (Ryngaert 1991, 112), given that he is “constructed in (several) parts” (Ubersfeld 1996, 93).

All the analyst is required to do in terms of characterisation is express a highly concerted interest in the information contained in the dramatic text in relation to the character’s clothing, how they move, their actions, their spatial relationships with others and the set, what they say, what others say to them, what others say about them, and the reactions of others to everything they say and to their actions (Vigeant 1989, 166).

The students were divided into several reading groups to analyse *The Soldier*. A summary of the teams’ work as a whole revealed a critical discourse entirely unfavourable to the character under scrutiny. It should not be forgotten that his title and the description of his costume in the initial stage directions immediately indicate that “*The Soldier*” embodies a militaristic political power that spreads terror and death; however, his relationship with others and the discourse of which he is the subject or object further strengthen this assessment. In fact, in the analysis of his relationship with other characters, the students and teacher were primarily interested in two particular pairings: *The Poet/The Soldier* and *The Soldier/The People*. Within these pairings, the intrinsic character traits of *The Soldier* are revealed to be pride and arrogance, aggression and violence. And the students made an evidential list of supporting statements, some of which were verbal – “Your slander will make me cut out your tongue” (Bodelin 2015, 25) or “Your head will roll, such malicious gossip” (ibid., 63) – and some of which were paraverbal or non-verbal: “he thumps his chest” (ibid., 24), “gets up, stamping the floor with his boot” (ibid., 41), “Berating” (ibid., 69), etc. Thanks to this diverse evidence relating to speech, voice and movement, it can be concluded that *The Soldier*’s whole being is imbued with violent and aggressive qualities. With this reputation, all that can be expected of him is a type of power that disseminates fear and terror, to intimidate *The People* and leave them with no other choice but to applaud and praise the despot and his leadership. The following exchange certainly suggests this quite forcibly:

The Poet: People! People! *The Soldier* is calling for you. Show yourselves right now, or you’ll face the baton. [*General commotion among spectators. Then silence.*]

The Poet: People! People! Show yourselves. [*A group of people draws away from the crowd and noisily stands in front of The Poet.*]

The Poet: Approach, followers! The Soldier is asking for you.

The People: [*Together*] We're frightened. We heard someone was threatened with death.

The Poet: Don't be scared, lowlife. Enter the hall. [*The People follow The Poet. As soon as he sees The Soldier, he starts applauding and cheering ...*]

The People: Long live The Soldier! Woyé, Woyé, Woya, Woya! Long live The Soldier! Woyé, Woyé, Woya, Woya! Soldier hééé ... Soldier haaa ... (Bodelin 2015, 60–61)

Clearly, the evidence, how it was organised and the subsequent student commentaries painted a very sombre picture of the dictator and his power.

When presenting their commentaries in the lecture hall, the students used a process of denial, the format of which can be seen in the following few examples: “The character we’re going to speak about has no characteristics in common with anyone currently in government and our comments should not be addressed to them”; “We’re going to speak about the qualities of a political leader and his regime that have nothing to do with what happens on campus these days. So, those currently in charge should not feel targeted”; “Our analyses and comments concern a political character and power that both come from the imagination of a writer who is not, incidentally, Beninese, and who wrote this play many years ago.” To all appearances, these discursive precautions reject any relationship, even indirectly, between the addressees (the other students and teacher) and those in power, instigators of a censorship that exists in public spaces, one of which is the Abomey-Calavi university campus. The students therefore did not target those in power in their critiques, formed through the analysis of the play in question. And anyway, in context, these methods acquired the status of false denials and thus established a communicational trope known to be actualised “each time the addressee who, in accordance with markers of speech, is primarily seen as a direct addressee, when in fact he only constitutes a secondary addressee” (Kerbrat-Orecchioni 1998, 132). During the presentation of their work, each team of students had direct addressees – namely, the other students and teacher. However, by conducting their oral presentation using methods similar to those mentioned above, the speakers used false denials to make those in power the primary addressees for their comments. The communicational subterfuge was so well perceived by all

that, in most cases, as soon as the speaker announced that the character their team was going to analyse dramaturgically had no resemblance to those who are in charge now, the whole lecture hall burst into knowing laughter. Because of this, the educational exercise of developing and reporting back on the analysis of a theatrical character became a convoluted way of speaking to the censors about the liberties they could not ordinarily and openly talk about without running the risk of severe reprisals – according to consistent testimonies – as such information was bound to be reported by intelligence agents concealed among the students, unbeknown to both them and their teachers. So, it was possible to avoid the constraints of censorship when studying the different characters.

The same opportunity arose when examining the plot, and more precisely the conclusion of *Le Compte-rendu*, which was the focus of the last class. Comparatively speaking, the importance of the conclusion in constructing a play's meaning is decisive. In fact:

when the curtain lowers, a situation has been reached that ... is the most important: it is the consequence of all the others shown during the play, it justifies them, it also justifies the events the characters have experienced ... And "the rest is silence". From that moment, we understand that the playwright attaches so much importance to this final scene. (Larthomas 2007, 128)

Hence, the conclusion is like a spotlight illuminating backwards, revealing to the reader the real meaning of each occurrence, each situation that has forged the action of the play.

When applying instructions for analysing the plot of Bodelin's play, the students reached a general consensus regarding their assessment of the following extract of dialogue, seeing it as crucial to the conclusion:

The People: We're frightened of The Soldier.

History: [*Go before The Soldier, remove his stripes and all his medals*] I have taken away all The Soldier's powers. Here he is, just like you. Speak, band of hypocrites!

The People: [*Jump up in a disorderly fashion, crying out in jubilation*] Woyé, woyé woyé! Bé, Bé, Bé! Ebééé! Ebééé! This is too good to be true! Did you hear? The Soldier no longer has power! Long live History! (Bodelin 2015, 68)

The Soldier is then stripped of his symbols of power, abruptly losing all the authority he held over The People. Fear has now changed camp, and the citizens, previously oppressed by liberticidal power, are now on their feet shouting unceremoniously at The Soldier: “This is the final scene of a comedy that’s lasted far too long” (Bodelin 2015, 68). The students were eager to pass commentary on the retorts quoted above. Moreover, there was a tendency to read and re-read the phrases, and some teams even tried to act out the scene, doing impromptu performances that produced an almost genuine cathartic pleasure at the demise of the real-life sovereign, experienced vicariously through the decline of the fictional despot. Aside from this “liberation” from real-life oppressive conditions through the cathartic effect of this fictional play, there is another, more important, issue that suggests that these retorts, decisive in the end, reveal the moral and civic awareness of each young reader that, ultimately, the people are the only real reason a leader remains in power or suffers his demise. In this particular case, through the analysis of *Le Compte-rendu*, a revolution took place when The People realised that the myth of the all-powerful and untouchable Soldier existed only in the mind. As soon as The People, supported by History, succeeded in shattering the myth, The Soldier could be returned to the reality of his limitations. This certitude then paved the way for an alliance of individuals – once at odds with each other – centred around common interests to which all people aspire. This didactic effect, inferred by the students under the guidance of their teacher, corresponds to the communicational function of art, which:

does not simply begin the moment the isolated reader becomes a “participant in the story by associating with other individuals whose efforts go in the same direction”. It is already at play when the reader, to all intents and purposes, adopts certain norms, certain expectations, and he learns, through aesthetic identification, what the experience and the role of others can be, the whole lot being able to determine his behaviour in terms of imitating models, certainly, but also in the sense of conscious motivation and the change in his experience to come. (Jauss 1978, 286)

In the context of a campus and country affected by violations of freedom, educational activities based on the play entitled *Le Compte-rendu* provided the students and teacher with a good reason to critique those in power without taking too much of a risk. They even experienced vicariously the present-day censors’ loss of power and authority. To this dual benefit, a third must be added, one that is even more important: the development of an awareness that can facilitate change and lead to a society liberated from violations of freedom.

Conclusion

This study is part conjecture: the pedagogical activities dedicated to the analysis of the play entitled *Le Compte-rendu* integrated strategies for the circumvention of censorship and for criticism of the masked dictatorship that teachers and students are confronted with on the Abomey-Calavi university campus in Benin. Participant observation was required to verify this conjecture, especially as I was involved in the educational activities in question.

Dramaturgical analysis and the Horizon of Expectation – inspired, in particular, by the works of Louise Vigean and Michel Pruner – also provided a foundation for discussion. By employing this methodological combination, the study showed how combining the initial content of the theatrical paratext with facts from the situational experience of student-readers helped to draw out markers of their Horizon of Expectation. From the analysis carried out and commentaries formulated by the students throughout this pedagogical experience, it seems that the analysis of a dramatic text, chosen purposefully, offers an opportunity to circumvent censorship by critiquing real-life abuse of power through that of fiction, to experience cathartic satisfaction thanks to the fall of the dictator, and to contribute to the progressive development of a keen awareness regarding the decline of ideological and symbolic infrastructures of liberticidal power. Nevertheless, the impact of these experiences remains very limited: strategies and discourse related to circumventing censorship were visible and audible only during the pedagogical activity itself and within the lecture hall. The impact of such an educational experience would be strengthened if it were to last longer and, for example, if it were carried out alongside the production and performance of a show inspired by Bodi Banche Bodelin’s play.

Acknowledgements

This article is part of a project that has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement no. 949378).

References

Apédo-Amah, Ayayi Togoata. 1997. “Bodi Banche Bodelin et Sélom Komlan Gbanou: pour un théâtre iconoclaste.” *Notre Librairie* 131: 162–169.

- Apédo-Amah, Ayayi Togoata. 2015. “Le théâtre au rendez-vous du jugement de l’histoire.” In *Le Compte-rendu*, by Bodi Banche Bodelin. Lomé: Éditions Awoudy.
- Bodelin, Bodi Banche. 2015. *Le Compte-rendu*. Lomé: Éditions Awoudy.
- Bush, Ruth, and Claire Ducournau. 2020. “Introduction. African Audiences: Making Meanings across Media.” *Research in African Literatures* 51 (1): vii–xv.
- Genette, Gérard. 1987. *Seuils*. Paris: Éditions du Seuil.
- Hounzandji, Aimé Frédéric. 2017. “Une Université dans un processus de construction nationale: L’Université du Dahomey-Bénin en Afrique occidentale (1950–2002).” PhD diss., Université Paris-Sorbonne.
- Hounzandji, Dédjinnaki Romain. 2016. “La Dramaturgie de la déviance dans le théâtre béninois et togolais des années 1990 à 2010.” PhD diss., Université d’Abomey-Calavi.
- Jauss, Hans Robert. 1978. *Pour une esthétique de la réception*. Translated by Claude Maillard. Paris: Gallimard.
- Kerbrat-Orecchioni, Cathérine. 1998. *L’Implicite*. Paris: Armand Colin.
- Larthomas, Pierre. 2007. *Le langage dramatique, sa nature, ses procédés*. Paris: Quadrige.
- Médéhouégnon, Pierre. 2010. *Le théâtre francophone de l’Afrique de l’ouest des origines à nos jours*. Cotonou: CAAREC Éditions.
- Popovic, Pierre. 2014. “De la semiosis sociale au texte: la sociocritique.” *Signata* 5: 153–172.
- Pruner, Michel. 2010. *L’analyse du texte de théâtre*. Paris: Armand Colin.
- Ryngaert, Jean-Pierre. 1991. *Introduction à l’analyse du théâtre*. Paris: Bordas.
- Thomasseau, Jean-Marie. 1984. “Pour une analyse du para-texte théâtral: quelques éléments du para-texte hugolien.” *Littérature* 53: 79–103.
- UAC. 2017. *Annuaire des statistiques de l’année académique 2015–2016*. Abomey-Calavi: Service des Statistiques, Université d’Abomey-Calavi (UAC).

Ubersfeld, Anne. 1996. *Lire le théâtre I*. Paris: Éditions Belin.

Vigeant, Louise. 1989. *La lecture du spectacle théâtral*. Laval: Mondia Éditeurs.

¹ Aimé Frédéric Hounzandji established that, in the past, student action could have a serious impact on the transformation or reconfiguration of the Beninese political microcosm. In his thesis, he states that “the university strike of 6 May 1985 and the social tension that followed in May and June noticeably unsettled the revolutionary power wielded by Mathieu Kérékou for almost thirteen years” (Hounzandji 2017, 334).

² The lecturer formerly held positions as a teaching assistant and then as assistant temporary lecturer in the Département de Lettres Modernes (Language and Literature Department) at the Université d’Abomey-Calavi, before being recruited to a permanent position in December 2018. In May 2019, he became Deputy Head of Department. As a teacher in higher education, he enjoys the freedom to choose educational topics as well as didactic and pedagogical aids, giving him free rein to identify which texts will be studied on the course entitled “Analyse du texte théâtral” (Theatre Text Analysis). With no political bias – i.e. not being a member of any political party – the lecturer considers that, while the current government may have carried out relevant reforms to administrative and financial governance, its management of issues regarding freedom of opinion and association is corrosive to certain principles of democratic government that Benin has nevertheless chosen since 1990.

³ According to official documents from the exam results board, 529 students were enrolled in the second year of Lettres Modernes during the 2018–19 academic year.

⁴ Out of all the UAC faculties, FLASH had the largest number of students. In October 2016, it was divided into two separate faculties: the Faculté des Lettres, Langues, Arts et Communication (Faculty of Literature, Languages, Arts and Communication) and the Faculté des Sciences Humaines et Sociales (Faculty of Human and Social Sciences).

⁵ This wording is taken from the Rector’s Decision no. 070-16/UAC/SG/VR-AARU/SA, dated 26 July 2016, pertaining to disciplinary sanctions imposed upon FLASH students, and also from the Rector’s Decree no. 484-2016/UAC/SG/CR/SP, dated 28 July 2016, pertaining to the invalidation of the 2015–16 academic year at FLASH.

⁶ On 24 March 2020, student leaders felt it was unacceptable to continue running lessons in overcrowded lecture theatres filled with students in close confinement while the Covid-19

pandemic spread terror worldwide and Africa was heading for ruin. A collective of students spontaneously formed a surveillance team and roamed the Abomey-Calavi campus to empty lecture halls of their studious populations. This operation incited police intervention. During the confrontation that followed, one student was hit by a bullet and died. Government authorities then instructed the police to withdraw from campus.

⁷ Created at different times during the history of the Université Nationale du Bénin (National University of Benin), renamed Université d'Abomey-Calavi, the three organisations that run alongside each other, sometimes clashing, at other times uniting around student militancy, are: the Fédération Nationale des Étudiants du Bénin (Benin's National Federation of Students), the Union Nationale des Étudiants du Bénin (Benin's National Union of Students) and the Union Nationale des Scolaires et Étudiants du Bénin (National Union of Schoolchildren, Pupils and Students).

⁸ According to Jean-Marie Thomasseau, the paratext is “this printed text (in italics or another font, always differentiating it visually from other parts of the work) that surrounds the dialogue in a piece of theatre” (1984, 79).

⁹ Michel Pruner defines the paratext as a “personal intervention, through which creators attempt to make their voice heard. To a text that can only be – as one will see – exterior to them, they add a paratext that specifies their intentions and reveals their aesthetic choices” (2010, 18).

¹⁰ Thomasseau's suggested approach may appear quite original; however, it introduces several problematic concepts. For initial stage directions to be considered as part of the paratext, it removes them all from the rest of the text, even the expressive opening stage directions that only make sense in close proximity with the dialogue.

¹¹ Here we might refer to Gérard Genette.

¹² RFI (Radio France Internationale) is a public French radio station broadcasting internationally, including to many large towns and cities across Africa, notably Francophone Africa. In 1975, RFI took over the organisation of the Concours théâtral interafricain (InterAfrican Theatre Competition), which launched in 1967 to promote theatre productions from Africa and the Indian Ocean.

¹³ FESTHEF is the Festival de Théâtre de la Fraternité (Fraternity Theatre Festival), organised in Lomé, and elsewhere, to promote young African creatives.

¹⁴ The Timonier National is a name given to former president Gnassingbé Eyadéma, who ruled Togo from 1967 until his death in 2005.

¹⁵ The conceptual and notional device in reception aesthetics incorporates the theory known as the Horizon of Expectation; this concept can be divided into two types, the second of which is examined in this study: the Social Horizon of Expectation. Hans Robert Jauss defines it as “a pre-comprehension of the world and life ... The reader’s pre-comprehension includes concrete expectations relating to a Horizon of interests, desires, needs and experiences as determined by the society and class they belong to as well as their individual history” (1978, 284).

¹⁶ By tropic, we mean a discourse in which profound meaning is displaced by immediate, primary meaning, referred to by the terms that allowed this discourse to be constructed.